

SOCIAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF REALITY IN SOVIET DOCUMENTARY FILM (IN CASE OF GEORGIA)

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Abstract

Georgian documentary film making has a rather rich tradition. The stated thesis is confirmed by the first full length documentary film “Akaki’s trip to Racha-Lechkhumi” recognized all over the world (1912, Director Vasil Amashukeli). Origination of the documentary film in Georgia is solely connected with the name of Vasil Amashukeli. A history started earlier in 1908 continues existence in propagandistic tongs resulted by the Soviet occupation of 1921. Surely, the sovietized Georgian documentary film making was not able to avoid the dictate’s influence. Ideologized news films were reflecting interpreted reality, which, in fact, had no any connection with the political, economic and cultural processes happening in the socius. Holidays, parades, urban development, agricultural achievements, industry and production – all this was delivered to the mass in the form of a documentary film and created ideal demonstration of the Soviet living conditions. However, despite of repressions Georgian authors managed to create the material carrying definite visual and content-related values that for the contemporary society with a definite accuracy revives daily routines of that period, challenges existing in front of the country, socio-economic background, political processes.

Keywords: Documentary Film, Soviet Union, Georgia.

Introduction

The series of the “Great October Socialistic Revolution” of 1917 were crowned with creation of the Soviet Union in 1922. After deposition of tsarism, Government of Russia was occupied by Bolsheviks (Social-Democratic Workers Party), who exactly considered the extent of significance of spreading of their ideas and concepts for preservation of the power in the center as well as in regions. The Leader of the Communist Party, Vladimir Lenin’s key task was interpretation of his own socialistic views and their delivery to the crowds in an easily understood language. The Soviet leader thoroughly acknowledged significance of subordination of the fields effecting the social consciousness to the Bolsheviks’ party. Accordingly, censorship also had been legalized and the first victim of this new order, on top of theater, literature and press, surely, became the cinema.

Under the Decree “About control over the film making” issued in March of 1918, private film makers were subordinated to the local councils. Since the year of 1919 all film studios were transferred under control of the government. “According to their policy, a film was deemed useless if it was not reporting a new idea stimulating mass opinion”. (Rotha, 1960, page 219).

Educational function of the film making was very essential on top of the propagandistic function. Similarly with Germany, since the end of 20s, ethnographic, expeditive and historic documentary film making became actual in the Soviet Union as well, being a re-

source of dissemination of a desirable knowledge. Accordingly, almost all films created in the communistic reality were devoted to the routine life of the audience, its social needs, comparison of the tsarism-related regime and the post-revolution period. After observing of a similar content, the audience, instinctively, appropriated the state social, industrial and cultural progress. Stage direction, ways of film making and montage, author’s ideas of that period were proceeding from the simple routine life of the viewer. Screen adaptation of actuality of their contemporary life and film making of the routine caused a feeling of effortlessness and trust in representatives of all generations.

“Due to full using of cinema’s resources, the Soviet film is able to effect the mental state and life attitudes. In fact, it is generated exactly for this purpose”. (Rotha, 1960, p.218).

Instinctively, Georgian film making passes to the control of similar communistic views after its sovietization in 1921. In two months after occupation of the 25th February, in April of 1921 a Section of cinema was opened in the People’s Education Commission. That time the cinema section had only one recording apparatus, an atelier consisting of three lighting devices and a laboratory of the operator Aleksandre Dighmelov.

For avoiding of a financial deficiency, the joint stock company of the state cinema industry was founded in 1923. With the support of the Georgian Education Commission, Higher Economic Council, Custom Administration, Agricultural Bank, Tbilisi Executive Commission and state commercial organizations

the shareholders contributions provided an opportunity for broadening of the film making". (Amirejibi, 1998, p.107) Based on structural changes, the cinema section was formed into a separate organization "Sakh-kimretsvi" which starts an active work.

Methodology

To demonstrate dynamics of development of the Georgian documentary film making in the Soviet reality we will apply methods of content analysis and historic analysis.

For consequential representation of challenges existing in that period in front of the national film making, on top of the existing scientific literature, we got acquainted with the press of the Soviet period kept in the Georgian national library, mainly newspapers "Soviet Art", "Flag".

By means of the content analysis we represented trends dominating in terms of the communistic governance, narrative, technical and imaginative values of the Soviet documentary film making.

We analyzed the film making reflecting the epoch based on the following criteria: content, style, means of imagination. From the thematic or audio-visual viewpoints, we analyzed documentary film making of the Soviet period, film materials carrying specific creative values, reflecting the epoch created from the occupation in 1921 – till 90s.

Discussion and results

"The Georgian documentary film tried to report all fields of life, to review and to refer to all topics and issues, which completely appeared as a confirmation of illusive existence of the country. Broadcasting of large-scaled constructions and activities on the display underscored strength and power of the Soviet order. (Levanidze, 2010).

The Soviet propagandistic films, from the content's viewpoint, may be allocated in several categories. In the initial period of sovietization, chronicles and events reflecting the routine life was much more actual which were underlying the benefit of the post-revolution period, restoration, stability. For instance: "Ceremony of the three year anniversary of the Caucasian 11th Army in Tbilisi", "Sending of children to Kojori on holidays", "Zahesi", "Construction of the Natakhtari Water Pipeline" and others. The enlisted materials represent classical documentary pictures. They are materials which saved significant facts of that period for history.

From the end of 20s authors start representing of definite attitudes towards definite events. The dry film chronicle is gradually replaced by the materials showing relevant trends, which were creative and targeted.

The film "Their Kingdom" (1928) represents a similar different form of delivery of author's messages to the audience. Despite of the fact that the film is a debut work of the first Georgian film director-woman, Nutsa Ghoghoberidze, it represents a result of a montage of film chronicle which had been recorded before. With similar creative approaches Mikheil Kalatozishvili, in cooperation with his co-authors, created a video material of documentary value which was described in the magazine "Memartksheneoba": "The chronicle

made by us represents a contradiction between activity of the Menshevik's state and the Soviet reality ... Here, a method of finishing is remarkable, which was serving as a guidance while assembling of the image, it is a parodism". According to explanations of the authors, due to the synthesis of neutral materials recorded by Mensheviks and contemporary cadres the material had lost the "primaevial semantics". "Here, neutral cadres and moments have no place. Thus, we prepared not a chronicle given by merely chronologically arranged moments, but a chronicle, where the plot is reached by means of montage and carries the whole idea – represents a film play." (Kalatozishvili & Ghoghoberidze, picture film-chronicle, 1928, page 57).

Except for "Their Kingdom" this documentary film is also titled "18-28" solely due to the conflict between the stated epochs. For instance, official events organized by the government of the Georgian Independent Republic are reflected in the material, which are followed by real routine cadres about difficult working conditions and exporting of the Georgian products. Here, one can see a visit of the second International Leaders of 1920 in Georgia and against the background of these ceremonies marine battles and breaking up of demonstrations are shown. In the film chronicle authors simultaneously with the official events and meetings use rather heavy cadres of difficult life conditions of the class of workers, ordinary citizens (including deceased citizens). By this kind of trending assembling, they show a real face of governors, as well as their real efforts for improving of the existing social conditions. The author's analysis, dependence upon the material, opinion and objective are vividly represented in the film for the first time in the Georgian reality.

"Film making is an art of technics. Merely here rationalization is possible for 100%. Not only from the viewpoint of recording and the laboratory actuality, but on the base of the art production. A task of the revolutionary film making is to create a methodology on processing of the material which will be aimed with the emotional and organizational art." (Kalatozishvili, Methods of showing of film material, 1928, page 34).

The archive film chronicle's montage is resulted in the Siko Dolidze's film "The 12th year of October". By way of showing of the decade of the Soviet state, the director represented difficulties of the pre-revolution life in one film, as well as the war, conflicts and the period of a peaceful labor after the October Revolution of 1917. Lenin's speeches, rapid restoration of the destroyed infrastructure, training battles of the Red Army, symbolic transferring in the beginning of the film which is represented with constant disorders ending with stability and happiness reflected in the final cadres.

A principle of the conflict between "old" and "new" is developed in the film "Poem on Shirak" (1931). Director Shalva Khuskivadze shows to the audience formation of the community on the Shirak lowland in the previous and following periods. Poverty of the population is changed upon adopting of a new order, all people start working, and opportunities obtained by the Soviet order bring welfare to the village. Symbolic demonstration of the routine of that period, film's dynamics and rhythm thoroughly represent a real

face of the *socius*. Constant competition for obtaining of a cooperative harvest and the workers' influence in the process of progressing of environmental conditions are the two narrative lines which reveal the Soviet reality with the author's interpretation.

Collectivization, mechanization and contemporary distribution of the working process are covered by the Siko Dolidze's film "Land's Call" (1929). Staged fragments of the film by showing of contemporary technics, an attempt of comparing of ancient instruments of labor with the new technologies using the associated montage, showing of the workers' conditions in the Soviet reality by symbolic episodes, totally, represent an agitated character of the picture and clearly reflects an attempt of showing of the reality to viewers under a desirable angle.

On top of the discussed instances, in 20-30s other documentary films definitely reflecting creative trends existing in Georgia of that period were shoot. Dziga Vertovi's "Film-eye", - a film making of the subject of routine life and real incidents represented a leading working approach for authors. Translation of current political and householding incidents, comparing of the past experience and contemporary actuality, being a given narrative line is dominating in the film making of the Sovietized country.

"As you sow, so you reap" (1930, Kote Mikaberidze); "Ten minutes in the morning" (1931, Aleksandre Jaliashvili); "Hygiene of the Collective Farmer" (1934, Vakhtang Shvelidze) and others. Similar agitating films majorly carry chronical, historic and educational-methodological character. The stated direction is called "Culture Films". Namely the documentary film making has an educational-propagandistic target. In 10s of the twentieth century impact of kinds of the film formed in Germany and their significance had been acknowledged thoroughly in the Soviet reality. Accordingly, similar materials are often used for strengthening of power and affecting on mass.

From the beginning of 30s poetic experiences appear in the Georgian documentary film making. The given thesis is confirmed by the fiction-documentary film "Jim-Shvante" directed by Mikheil Kalatozishvili. After "Their Kingdom", the author once again continued revealing of peculiarities of events using innovative means. Currently, majority of researchers agrees that the film "Salt to Svans" is not the film showing only hard life conditions of residents of Ushguli and difficulties of the *socius* remained without salt. Each exactly acknowledged cadre of the film is targeted at showing to the viewer of an effect of innovation and progress in the process of relevant development of the society.

Finding of a "point of view" is of a key importance with a kind of visual angle "line of sight" where expression of the material will be maximally represented in the special forms. The line of sight should not make an original from the subjects or to finish them. It should act as a stylistic mean which will be reasonably targeted in connection with the plot's order". (Kalatozishvili, Methods of showing of film-material, 1928, page 36).

The film's author, using the realized line of sight of scenes, represents the environment with comparative

reality and accent, by correct compositive structuration of images. Recording of Svan's towers from bottom to top, backlight cadres, details and panoramas is the author's mean for providing of viewers not only with dry facts, but with the contently enriched image as well. The stated theory is confirmed with the cadres of extracting of stones for building of towers, movement of the camera while recording of the given complicated process; composition represented in mutual, average and detailed views illustrates complexity and hardness of the routine work. Another one instance is the fragment of plies combing and knitting. The camera installed on the machine-tool brace in prospects shows a face of the Svan woman, monotonous movement of her hands that, in combination creates an impression of mechanic, exhausting and bored labor among viewers. Similar technic is repeated in other scenes illustrating the working process.

While correct perceiving of the image, exposition of the cadre is also essential. The film's author called the light "an instrument of impression". Using this "instrument" he created impressive pictures of that period – Svan's towers, glaciers, backlight cadres and shadow-figures.

The next aspect, which turns the author's sight much clearer, and the form of message more poetic and esthetic is the technics of the montage. Mikheil Kalatozishvili considered that the "film material is represented by subjects of the physical world existing around us. Culture of these subjects dictates to us relevant means and style of processing" (Kalatozishvili, Methods of showing of film materials, 1928). As it was explained by him the film base is applied for the similar stylistic order – light, optics and movement. This is the way of creation of a full image to satisfy the "social order". This technic provides continuity of movement, a chain of events that, together shows a complexity of the situation and context of a whole picture.

Scenes of death and birth are shown by way of paralleled montage, as well as hardness and acuteness of the contradictory events reflected in traditions. In the episode of horse riding, dynamic replacing of cadres, correct and consequential location of the line of sight creates a feeling of continuity of the process. Illustration of the staged events with similar style makes the picture more realistic, it makes you to be a participant of the scene and emotionally involves into the process. Feeling of movement, followed by the scenes of throwing stones, riding horse and working, results in a definite attraction in the viewer. Rhythm of images does not give a possibility to relax and forces to see the scenes up to the end.

Revealing of the author's individual attitude to the issues, diversity of means and methods of illustration was reflected on another direction of the documentary film making. In 30-40s historical-biographic films, reporting materials, film novels and film sketches appear.

It is important, that directors, on the example of a routine of key heroes, generalize advantages of transferring from the primitive – to the contemporary technologies. One of such examples is the film "Silk" (1932, G. Gomarteli). It is the ancient methods of "silk making" shown on one example of one woman. By comparing of the similar hard-working process with the

silk making factory the author shows to the audience efficiency of the socialistic order and contrast with the past.

We should separately mention the biographic films: "Memory to a Great Poet" (1935); "Ilia Chavchavadze" (1937); "Shota Rustaveli" (1938), "Memory to Sergo Orjonikidze" (1940). It is the period when the most important mean of representation in the documentary film making – a voice appears. The audience listens to the creative works of Akaki Tsereteli, Ilia Chavchavadze, Shota Rustaveli staged in the film via music. Application of the stated instrument became a key instrument of transmission, accenting of the idea and creation of a desirable emotion for the author.

Irakli Kandelaki's film "Tbilisi" (1939) illustrates the city's life. A viewer starts a trip in the capital by replacing of long-termed panoramas and views. The documentary film makes efforts to show the Tbilisi life by representing of almost all activities with maximal accuracy from morning – till night.

By walking with tourists, the city's museum and the artefacts kept in them are shown. Accent is made on culture, sport events, state universities and library. From the ethnographic museum we move to the Kote Marjanishvili's stage play "Solar Eclipse in Georgia". In this form the author shows to the viewer the theatric life and character of the old Tbilisi. Finally, the following landscapes are displayed: Botanic Garden, Funicular, Lisi Lake, noisy streets and night capital. "Genre of the film is chronical-documentary, the principle is comparison of time, rhythm and scale". (Zhvania, 1990, p.70).

In addition to the given directions scientific-popular films appeared on the screen of that period was devoted to the medicine. The following film novels were prepared regarding the actual problems of medicine of the past century and ways of their solving: "Malaria", "Rubella", "Enteric Fever".

Since 40s, the key task of the film making in the period of war was, similarly with other directions of means of the mass communication, keeping of historic cadres showing military actions, supporting of the army, demoralization of the enemy and informing of the society about the military front life.

It is particularly noteworthy that the newly appeared voice in the film making was supplemented with noise. The audience listened to the noise of mortar guns, air planes, scattershot, that made the image much more easily perceivable, and the content – more emotional.

If we judge with the stated characteristic features one of the most distinctive film is "General Chanchibadze's Gvardia in the last battles of the Patriotic War" (1945). The attached noise fully complies with each image in the military actions recorded under direction of Giorgi Asatiani. "Recently, making of a plot is usual and natural, but that time merging of a definite sound synchronically with the image and its approaching to the reality was the first attempt". (Zhvania, 1990, p.90).

„Attack of our soldiers in the suburbs of Orjonikidze", "Tracing the fascist beasts", "Post of the Black Seal", "Marine Battle", "Sevastopol's heroes", "Patriot fishers", "Front-related spring in Georgia", "Strong Friendship" – this is an incomplete list of battles shoot

in the period of war which reflect the processes happening on the front and hard housekeeping terms of the population left far from the military actions.

The first decade after the Patriotic War for the Georgian documentary film making, from the creative or imaginative viewpoint, was not distinctive. Authors did not use innovatory, experimental approaches in the working process. Film making of the stated period is a dry mirror of events which is followed by the surficial explanation of the speaker. Chronicle films majorly are devoted to industry, technologies, and labor conditions, agricultural and scientific development. The system required from the film director constation of facts, dry and surficial description. Individualism, creative narrative and analysis were replaced by description of the declared forms of the collective image, popularization of achievements of the "successful" republic, ideologized interpretation of the existing reality.

Since the mid 50s, the documentary film making repeatedly shows diversity of forms. Authors gradually transfer from the chronical film making on the author's films. It is the period when the first poetic forms appear.

In 1958, the Film Chronicle Sector of the "Sakkinmretsvi" was transformed into the studio of documentary and scientific-popular films. Despite of the fact that the documentary film making of that period was less popular in comparison with the fiction cinema, it still managed to build innovative views, style and attitudes on the experience counting forty years. The stated opinion is confirmed by the historical-creative films, sport and scientific sketches, reporting materials from different regions. For instance, "Trip to Nepal", "A story of one attempt", "On the trace of Mtkvari", "To the Tyanshan peak", "Hunting in Jungles", "My village", "Cast iron".

One of the most important examples of representation of definite themes poetically by authors is the film "Sapovnela" (1959, scene author – I. Khutsishvili, operator – A. Semionov). Otari Ioseliani's short-termed film narrates about the florist Mikheil Mamulashvili, who has been taking care over rare plants and cultivating new species for 80 years. From the first second of the film the viewer pays attention on a composition of flowers. Each image reflecting activity of the old gardener opens a magic environment for the viewer's sight. Audio-visual characteristic cadres of imagination, the narrator's voice, sounds harmonize and replace each other that makes the material much more clearly perceivable.

Here, we should mention the means of montage which are used today in the contemporary film making. A technic of transferring from one cadre to another, continuity of movement, focusing on details, logical replacing of dimensions, esthetics of the multi-layer cadre and harmonization with music illustrates an activity of the old gardener with a gasp.

In addition to the stated, parallels with the ancient Georgian culture, music changes and the so called "voice over" delivers one of the key messages of the film to the audience stating that the main teacher of the art is nature. Audio-visual features, means and technics of representation makes the film "Sapovnela" the most important example of the Georgian documentary film

making of the Soviet period. Combination of a narrative and imaginative side of the film represents experimental, but well-known and adapted methods for the contemporary society.

Example of a repeated realizing of the issue creatively is the film "White Torgva" (1969). The author Gia Chubabria narrates about the period passed with the Tush sheep breeders and shows the difficult way from the winter pastures to the summer farm. Compared with contemporary forms, the film with its style looks like the documental film making in observational mode. Without symbolism, the director demonstrates the processes which happen really. Each line of sight and view is preliminary decided. The noise used with the music forces the viewer to participate in the process. Cadres of the short-termed film, with their composition and esthetics added a poetic appearance to the work. A technic of the montage and the author's view show the problem more deeply than dry reporting film chronicle.

Example of the poetic, avant-garde documentary film making is Sergo Parajanov's "Arabesques on the theme of Pirosmeni" (1985). Using symbols, abstract cadres and non-standard narrative the author acquaints viewers with the tragic life and work of the artist.

The film is divided into several parts: "Tbilisi", "Photograph's atelier in Sololaki", "Pages of History", "Shamil", "Erekle II", "Tamari and horseman", "Animals", "Infertility and motherhood", "Holidays", "Bunch of flowers for Margarita", "Niko's requiem", "A step to eternity".

Heavy biography of Niko Pirosmenishvili inspires the author to deliver to the audience, using different means of expression, definite parts of the artist's sensitive, impulsive and lonely life. History of the country suggested in short sketches, pantomimes' episodes, dynamics of strong showing and narration of the painting create one mutual picture about tragedy of the Pirosmeni's life and his one of the key challenges – loneliness. Moreover, poetry of cinema is determined by the purposeful applying of music and noise.

A viewer can not hear voice of the heroes. Neither the so called "voice over" narrates by the artist's biography, but for the viewer the key message of each fragment becomes clear.

From the first minutes, photo atelier and posing of noble people against the musical background create one large satiric picture which is followed by the Niko Pirosmeni's photo and melancholic melody relevant with the mood. The audience exactly realizes the extent of tragedy of the artist's life and thoughts, compared with the life of rich people of that time.

During the whole film multiple Pirosmeni's images are shown on the screen. Replacing of details and general views, music, voices of animals, battles, drinking bouts and prayers revive, from one sight static graphical canvases in front of viewers.

The last scenes are particularly noteworthy. Pirosmeni's love story, a bouquet of roses presented to Margarita and the door, beneath of which, in the eternity, Pirosmeni becomes an integral part of contemporary life. Final cadre of the dying fish appeared on the molebut is a metaphor of the artist's life. A metaphor of painting found as a life belt in the routine stuffiness

which did not satisfy a thirst of avoiding of love and loneliness.

As like as mentioned in the titles "Arabesques", harmonization of forms and means of expression used in the film creates an integrity of the documentary film, which is continued beneath the frames of audience depiction.

Conclusion

In terms of the post-Soviet ideology, censure and strictly determined creative frames authors hardly managed to step in parallel with the trends existing beneath the "Iron Curtains".

If on the first stage the national documentary film making represented a mechanic reflection of the reality and retranslation of the current actual event, after 20s it obtains definite genre-related features and appears as the author's representation of reality. The Soviet documentary film making may be divided into several directions: films, which reflect comparison of the past and present; cinema, where effect of revolution on human beings is shown; reporting of significant events; scientific-popular film sketch.

In fact, the genre which had a potential for showing of real problems, social, cultural, or political processes found themselves in tongs of the ideology. In the country suffering from repressions of 1937 a main theme of the documentary film represented the idealized Soviet life. For instance: "Great October Revolution 20", "October's XXIII", "Autumn in Kakheti", "Aleksi Stakhanov in Georgia", "Georgian Resorts" and others. The society is acquainted with the people "constructing new reality", "Stakhanov-like worker Obolashvili", "Physician Kadagidze", "Operation of the Great Surgeon Professor Giorgi Mukhadze" and others.

To take a parallel with the world's trends, the Georgian documentary film a bit later and much more difficultly (with the account of the existing reality) was making steps of development on the creative way. Since 1910-1920s modernistic approaches dominating in the developed states were registered in the films of the pioneer authors, such as "Head hunting country", "Northern Nanuki", "Moana". Similar kinds of poetic experiments in the case of Georgia, for the first time, appeared in 30s in the works: "Jim Shvante", "Silk", and in 60s – "White Torgva", "Sapovnela".

On top of personal histories and traditions films devoted to urban development and life are noteworthy as well. In this aspect we may compare the film made in 1927 with co-authorship of Valter Ruthman, Carl Mayer, and Carl Fround "Berlin: symphony of a large city" and the film shoot in 1939 "Tbilisi".

After sovietization, Dziga Vertov and his manifest had a serious impact on Georgian authors. The stated approach was fully blocking romanticism, avant-garde and poetic attitudes. "Film-eye" and "Film-Truth", only with the cadres taken from reality, was creating a desirable content and disseminating it in the society. As it was mentioned above a part of the Georgia authors deemed the cinema as "the art of technics" in this way. A task of the revolutionary film making was creation of a kind of methodology of processing of materials which will be targeted with the emotional and organizational

art”. (Kalatozishvili, Methods of showing of film materials, 1928).

Despite of the fact that the Georgian documentary film was looking for the forms and means of depiction in ideological frames, with the support of concrete authors, it managed to obtain the world trends, to form its own genre or stylistic features, to find individual forms of expression of idea, to say own word on the worldwide scale and that is important, to create a solid basis for the future development.

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